

BAZI XUSUSIY INTEGRAL TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI YECHISHDA FREDGOLM USULI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada integral tenglamalarning kelib chiqish tarixi haqida qisqacha ma'lumotlar berilgan. Fredgolmning birinchi va ikkinchi tur integral tenglamalarining amaliy ahamiyati, uni yechish bo'yicha ketma-ket yaqinlashish hamda iteratsiyalangan yadrolar usullarini qo'llash yo'llari bayon qilingan. Bir nechta misollar yechib ko'rsatilgan, mustaqil bajarish uchun misollar tuzilgan va taqdim qilingan. Maqolani tayyorlashda mavzuning talabalarga tushunarli qilib yoritilishiga katta ahamiyat berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: integral tenglama, Furiye almashtirishi, ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar usuli, funksiya argumenti, Fredgolmning birinchi tur integral tenglamasi, Fredgolmning ikkinchi tur integral tenglamasi, iteratsiyalangan yadrolar usuli.

FREDHOLM'S METHOD FOR SOLVING A SYSTEM OF PARTIAL INTEGRAL EQUATIONS

Abstract. The article presents a brief history of the emergence of integral equations. The practical significance of the Fredholm integral equations of the first and second type, methods of successive approximation and repeated kernels for their solution are described. Several examples are illustrated, the examples are compiled and presented for self-fulfillment. When preparing an article, great importance is attached to ensuring that the topic is understandable to students.

Keywords: Fourier transform, method of successive approximations, function argument, Fredholm integral equation of the first kind, Fredholm integral equation of the second kind, method of iterated kernels.

МЕТОД ФРЕДГОЛЬМА РЕШЕНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫХ УРАВНЕНИЙ В ЧАСТНЫХ ПРОИЗВОДНЫХ

Аннотация. В статье дана краткая информация об истории возникновения интегральных уравнений. Описано практическое значение интегральных уравнений Фредгольма первого и второго рода, методов последовательного приближения и повторных ядер для их решения. Проиллюстрировано несколько примеров, примеры составлены и представлены для самостоятельного выполнения. При подготовке статьи большое значение придается тому, чтобы тема была понятна учащимся.

Ключевые слова: интегральное уравнение, преобразование Фурье, метод последовательных приближений, аргумент функции, интегральное уравнение Фредгольма первого рода, интегральное уравнение Фредгольма второго рода, метод повторных ядер.

Integral tenglamalar deb, noma'lum funksiya integral ishorasi ostida bo'lgan tenglamalarga aytiladi.

Mexanika, matematika fizika va texnikaning juda ko'plab masalalar ushbu

$$\varphi(x) - \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = f(x) \quad (1)$$

ko‘rinishdagi integral tenglamalarning tekshirishga olib kelinadi, bu erda $\varphi(x)$ – noma’lum funksiya, $K(x, y)$ va $f(x)$ funksiyalar mos ravishda $a \leq x \leq b$, $a \leq y \leq b$ va $a \leq x \leq b$ (a, b - o‘zgarmas sonlar) yopiq sohalarda berilgan uzluksiz haqiqiy funksiyalar. $f(x)$ funksiya (1) integral tenglamaning ozod hadi, $K(x, y)$ tenglmaning yadrosi, sonli λ ko‘paytuvchi tenglamaning parametri deyiladi.

Fredgol‘mning birinchi tur integlamasi deb,

$$\int_a^b K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = f(x) \quad (2)$$

ko‘rinishdagi integral tenglamaga aytiladi.

Agar (1) tenglamada $f(x) \equiv 0$ bo‘lsa, ya’ni

$$\varphi(x) - \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = 0 \quad (3)$$

tenglama (1) mos bo‘lgan bir jinsli integral tenglama deyiladi.

Bir jinsli

$$\varphi(x) - \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = 0 \quad (4)$$

tenglama (3) bir jinsli tenglamaga qo‘shma integral tenglama deyiladi.

$$\varphi(x) - \lambda \int_a^x K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = f(x), \quad x > a \quad (5)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘lsa, u Vol‘teraning ikkinchi tur integral tenglamasi,

$$\int_a^x K(x, y)\varphi(y)dy = f(x) \quad (6)$$

Tekshirib ko‘rish qiyin emaski, agar ikkinchi tur Fredgolintegral tenglamasining umumiy echimi $\Phi(x)$ mavjud bo‘lsa

$$\Phi(x) = \varphi^0(x) + \varphi(x) \quad (7)$$

ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladi, bunda $\varphi^0(x)$ (3) tenglamaning umumiy echimi,

esa (1) tenglamaning umumiy va xususiy echimlari bo‘lsa, bularning ayirmasi $\varphi^0(x) = \Phi(x) - \varphi(x)$

(3) tenglamaning echimidan iborat bo‘ladi. Bundan darhol (7) tenglik kelib chiqadi.

Fredgolm ikkinchi tur integral tenglamasini parametr kichik bo‘lganda ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan echish.

(1) tenglamani tekshiramiz, $K(x, y)$ va $f(x)$ funksiyalar o‘zlari aniqlangan sohalarda uzluksiz bo‘lgani uchun

$$\lambda \int_a^x |K(x, y)| \leq M, \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad \max_{a \leq x \leq b} |f(x)| = m \quad (8)$$

bo‘ladi.

Agar (1) tenglama λ parametr

$$|\lambda| < \frac{1}{M} \quad (9)$$

shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda bu tenglamalarning yagona $\varphi(x)$ echimi mavjud bo'lib, uni ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan topish mumkin.

Nolinchi yaqinlashish sifatida (1) tenglamaning ozod hadini qabul qilamiz

$$\varphi_0(x) = f(x)$$

Binchi yaqinlashishni

$$\varphi_1(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) f(y) dy$$

munosabat bilan aniqlaymiz. Bu jarayonni davom ettirib, n-yaqinlashishni

$$\varphi_n(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) \varphi_{n-1}(y) dy, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (10)$$

munosabat bilan aniqlaymiz.

Shunday qilib, (10) rekurrent munosabatlarni qanoatlantiruvchi

$$\varphi_0(x), \varphi_1(x), \dots, \varphi_n(x), \dots$$

funksional ketma-ketligiga ega bo'lamiz.

Matematik analizdan ma'lumki, (11) ketma-ketlikning yaqinlashishi

$$\varphi_0(x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\varphi_n(x) - \varphi_{n-1}(x)] \quad (12)$$

qatorning yaqinlashishiga teng kuchlidir. (10) formulani

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_n(x) &= f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) [\varphi_{n-1}(y) - \varphi_{n-2}(y) + \varphi_{n-1}(y)] dy = \\ &= f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) \varphi_{n-2}(y) dy + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) [\varphi_{n-1}(y) - \varphi_{n-2}(y)] dy = \\ &= \varphi_{n-1}(x) + \lambda \int_a^b K(x, y) [\varphi_{n-1}(y) - \varphi_{n-2}(y)] dy \quad n = 2, 3, 4, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz.

(8) ga asosan (13) dan quyidagi tengsizliklar kelib chiqadi:

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi_0(x)| &\leq m \\ |\varphi_1(x) - \varphi_0(x)| &\leq m|\lambda| M \\ |\varphi_2(x) - \varphi_1(x)| &\leq m|\lambda|^2 M^2 \\ &\dots\dots\dots \\ |\varphi_n(x) - \varphi_{n-1}(x)| &\leq m|\lambda|^n M^n \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib, (12) qatorning har bir hadi musbat sonli

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} m|\lambda|^n M^n$$

Ta'kidlash joizki, integral tenglamalar nazariyasi matematik fizika, differensial tenglamalar masalalarini hal qilishda keng qo'llaniladi. Jumladan, [3-15] ishlarda operatorli matritsalar uchun Fredgolm determinantini qurish, Fadeev tenglamasini qurish jarayonida integral tenglamalarni yechish usullaridan foydalanilgan. [16-36] ilmiy maqolalarda olib borilgan izlanishlarda aralash tipdagi tenglamalar uchun qo'yilgan chegaraviy masalalar Fredgol'mning ikkinchi tur tenglamasiga keltiriladi. Fredgol'mning ikkinchi tur tenglamasi yechimining mavjudligidan (tegishli shartlar ostida) chegaraviy masalaning ham yechimi mavjudligi haqida xulosa qilinadi.

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